

ECONOMIC AND SOCIAL IMPACTS OF MIGRATION ON MOROCCO-SPAIN RELATIONS

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Abstract:

Spain and Morocco are two nations that share more than cultural and historical legacies. Their geographical proximity and contemporary geopolitical realities shape their relationship. This article explores the multifaceted dynamics of their bilateral relations, with a particular focus on migration and its impact on socio-political, economic, and cultural exchanges. While migrant labor is indispensable for economic growth, there are policies that highlight the duality in perception towards migration. There are concerns like national security that guide those policies. Morocco's strategic role as both a source and transit country for migrants underscores its importance in regional geopolitics. This article also highlights the rise of a second generation of Spaniards with Moroccan roots, coupled with shared linguistic and cultural ties. However, socio-economic inequalities and discrimination impede the progress of their integration. Spain-Morocco relations need transcending policy debates to embrace migration as a cultural and economic bridge. Both these countries also need to have a critical perspective on the challenges and opportunities inherent in contemporary Spain-Morocco relations.

Keyword: Spain-Morocco, Migration, Geopolitics, Integration, Inequality

Economic and Social Impacts of Migration on Morocco-Spain Relations

Morocco has seen people moving more closely than any other country, as it has witnessed emigration since the early 1960s. However, it has also been receiving migrants not only from sub-Saharan countries but also from countries like Spain, where the economy is not doing very well and also from war-torn countries like Syria and Libya (Lahlou, 2015).

Morocco did not pay much heed to the outward migration from Morocco to Spain as it did not think it to be a problem for Spain. For such a small

country, there are around 3 million Moroccans who are living in different European countries like Belgium, Italy, Spain, Holland and France.

Moroccans, however, started paying more attention towards the border problem as their focus on regulations reflected their intention to exercise stringent measures to prevent illegal migration. In an interview with the leading Spanish daily 'el país', King Mohamed VI accepted in 2005 that they were aware of the repetitive requests from the Spanish government and had made changes in their policies accordingly. The Moroccan policies and the changes introduced in the 2000s saw the birth of institutions like the Directorate of Migration and Border Surveillance and the Migration Observatory.

Morocco and Spain saw some significant changes in the year 2006 when, after the violent attempts by migrants in the Spanish enclaves of Ceuta and Melilla in the north of Morocco, there were special corridors set between Morocco and the Canary Islands.

Historical Context

However, to understand more about the relations between Spain and Morocco, one has to dive deeper in the past. It's not just the current migratory patterns that influence the shaping of both these countries, but also a past with rich heritage that explains why these two neighboring nations share a special connection. As Arab kingdoms ruled Spain from the 8th to 15th century, it contributed towards the making of the modern Spanish race (Harbron, 1956). Due to special relationship that Spain shares with Morocco, its Muslim subjects are more loyal to Spain than the Muslims of other country towards them (Harbron, 1956).

Spain had a vast colonial presence in South America. However, towards the end of the nineteenth century a new world order was taking shape. After Spain lost its colonies and was defeated in the 1898 war, it shifted its focus towards North Africa and tried to make up for its losses by aiming to restore its prestige there.

If we take a closer look, we find that there were many people who were pro-Morocco. In fact, the most decorated Army veterans in Spain were Africanistas. There was a considerable presence of Spanish Army there and they treated it like their home. The ill-famed dictator General Francisco Franco also trained his forces in Spanish Morocco. The

Spanish Civil war broke out officially when Franco led its forces starting from there.

Not just people or culture, the language spoken in these two countries speak a lot about this special connection. Arabic and Spanish have a lot of things in common and this commonality owes a lot to the exchanges between these two languages. Spanish words have a heavy influence of Arabic. Even, some words are used in North Africa and Spain without any changes. *Jarabe* is a word, for example, that is used in both places. As there used to be Spanish officials who were in the Moroccan service, they used to speak Arabic fluently not only at their workplace but also inside their houses with their family members. As far as the identity of the Majority of Moroccans is concerned, one third of them are Berbers who speak Amazigh (Arango & Martin, 2005). Though, generally speaking, Morocco has Arabic as its official language.

Apart from historical and cultural perspective, Spain and Morocco came closer as a result of the prevalent world politics back then. There was a time when Britain and France had shunned Spain. It was not included in the United Nations. Besides, they were denied a big Aid under the Marshall program. In these conditions, Spain looked towards the middle East as an ally. This is also to note that other major European countries were not in good conditions in these lands. Morocco had a special place in the foreign policies of the Spanish government. It can be ascertained by the fact that the then-Spanish foreign minister visited the Middle East with the daughter of Franco, Carmen Franco, in 1952 (Harbron, 1956).

Migration Dynamics

To understand the migration dynamics, one has to look into early migration patterns, demographic shifts, and the settlement trends. Morocco is not just a country that is neighboring Spain and France. There are many inhabitants who speak Spanish and French frequently as Morocco is culturally rich in terms of multilingual setup.

The early migration patterns suggest that there was a lot of tourism from Africa to Europe, and various forms of mobility were being explored during that time. The geopolitics of Morocco has always been affected by the Migration policies made in the countries that were members of the European Union. One such policy was the "closing of the doors" in

Western Europe, which affected the Moroccan population on the move for many years (Juntunen, 2002).

Juntunen (2002) has also written about the real situation in the community of L'araish in Morocco, where it was found out that there was not a single house on the street that didn't have a migrant in Europe. There was a special mention of another name Terrassa, an industrial area in Catalonia, Spain. There was a lot of migration from the province of L'araish to Terrassa.

Migration flow was not always from Morocco to Europe. Europeans had been going to Morocco and northern African regions for a long period of time. According to estimates, the Maghreb population includes 15 percent of people who are of European origin (Stiftung, 2015). It wasn't for tourism in earlier days. Many impoverished people from Europe used to migrate to North Africa. There are some astonishing data that reveal the quantum of such migration from Europe to Morocco. If we compare data from the 20th century, there were more Germans on Moroccan soil than Moroccans in Germany (Stiftung, 2015).

Migration is not just happening between Morocco and other European countries. There are many migrants who use Morocco as a link between Africa and Europe. Given the conditions in Many Middle Eastern countries like Libya, people are migrating to Maghreb. They don't only migrate to settle there; they see the strong link between North Africa and Europe and know that it is a gateway for them, too.

Moroccans are known for their love of working in foreign lands. A certain part of their population has always been on the move. Almost 10 per cent of the Moroccan population has always worked overseas on a regular or temporary basis (Stiftung, 2015).

They moved alone in the beginning and then started settling there. What started as the migration of unmarried youth working as unskilled labourers, converted into settlements with their whole families living together. There were many local schools with Moroccan origin students. A lot of migration was not recorded by the officials. There was a lot of hidden migration from Morocco to Spain. Moroccans refer to the hidden migration with the Arabic term *hijra sirriya* (Juntunen, 2002). It tells how there has been unofficial migration apart from the official migration.

It is not surprising to see all this migration go undocumented. Spain had always allowed Moroccans to stay in its territories or let them pass to other neighboring European countries like France and Germany. Back then some Moroccans also saw Spain as a gateway to Europe. However, in May 1991, Spain started asking for visas for incoming Moroccans (Juntunen, 2002). Things started changing rapidly and it got escalated to another level. Another step the Spanish government took was the construction of double fences, which were four metres high. One interesting fact about this endeavor was the funding agencies behind it. This multi-million project was funded by the European Union.

No matter what measure were taken, there was a rise in the number of migrants. This increase in the number of migrants and the opening of visa systems for Moroccans to Spain saw the rise of *Harraga* smuggling, which is just the Arabic term for migrant smuggling between Moroccan ports like Casablanca and European ports (Juntunen, 2002).

Let us take a look at migration from the economic point of view. Labor trends also give us a new insight when talking about the migrant labour force in Spain. Migrants have to look for jobs in areas where they find it reasonable for them to be in. The distribution of unemployment rate is very disproportionate but those living in less job producing areas admit that they cannot simply afford to move to job offering places. This creates a huge gap.

Agricultural sector in Spain paints a different picture. There are hundreds of thousands of migrant labourers who work in farm sectors in Spain. Those that follow the traditional route, often go to the Rioja vineyards after completing the work in Catalunya. From there, they proceed to Valencia, where they work on oranges. In the end they go to places like Almeria and Murcia. So, there are many sectors where the migrant force is employed however, it is the agricultural sector which employs them the most (Arango & Martin, 2005). The migration pattern of Moroccans has also changed over the years. Earlier they used to go to more traditional places like Catalunya and Andalusia but now they also go to non-traditional destinations like Aragon and Navarra (Liu et al., 2019).

Irrespective of the demand for workers, the Spanish laws kept bringing legislative frameworks to keep them at bay. The Spanish migration policy saw an important change in 1985 when it enacted a law called

'Ley de Extranjera" (Arango & Martin, 2005). 'Ley' means law and 'Extranjera' means foreigner. It was that year only when Spain became member of EU. Through this law, it gained more control over regulation of migrants that were not from European Union.

However, Spain was not always averse to taking migrants. It ran a regularization program that continued for two years. This program gave legal sanctity to the stay of around 460000 migrants in 2002 (Arango & Martin, 2005). Of these, around 25 percent people were of Moroccan origin.

Giving them sanctity is one thing, but the hardships those immigrants go through is another story. Amongst many migrants that enter Spain, Africans share the saddest stories of all. Though Latin Americans enter through other countries like Amsterdam on tourist visas and Asians who enter also through Schengen visas issued by many other countries, most of the Africans arrive in small boats through the Strait of Gibraltar. Those boats are also called 'pateras'.

Those sad stories don't just end when they reach European mainland. They have to face many problems including conflicts with other peers. There is conflict amongst various migrant groups. In 2002 for example, the Moroccan migrants protested and there was a call for hunger strike in Sevilla. They claimed that the work in the strawberries sector was given to the East Europeans instead of Moroccans and Algerians (Arango & Martin, 2005). The employers claimed that they didn't have any other resort as they were being fined for employing illegal Moroccan workers while the Eastern Europeans had legal documents (Arango & Martin, 2005).

However, the story is different when we hear narrations from the other side. The employer associations have claimed repetitively that there were labour shortages in many sectors in Spain and welcomed the arrival of migrant workers in those sectors. No matter how hard the policies be towards Moroccans, it cannot be denied that the Spanish demand for Moroccan labor is going to go up (White, 2001).

Challenges in Bilateral Relations and Socio-Cultural Implications

The interplay of bilateral relations is very complex. Be it through constitution of different governmental bodies or small skirmishes, these countries face many challenges that have to be addressed by both the

countries. Spanish and Moroccans have been also fighting over an island called 'Isla de Perejil' by the Spaniards and 'Leila Island' by the people of Morocco. This war which was called a 'miniature' war by Martinez (2003) shows how ugly the situations have been between these two countries.

Gregory White (2001) has talked about the riots that occurred in Spain in the year 2000. 'El Ejido' witnessed deadly clashes. The death of a Spanish woman at the hands of a mentally disturbed Moroccan just gave spark to a wider anti Moroccan sentiment that had prevailed in those days. Gerard also goes on to explain the "push" and "pull" mechanism when it comes to Moroccans migrating to Spain. It is a question that has puzzled many researchers.

Though documenting the challenges in bilateral relations tell us about the measures each country has taken, investigating the socio-cultural implications give us a real insight into the actual situation. One of the aspects that can be covered to know about those socio-cultural implications is the post migration wedding scenarios. (Esteve & Bueno, 2012) referred to Spain's 2007 National Immigrant Survey to investigate the patterns that emerged out of post migration marriages in Spain.

It was interesting to know post the findings by (Esteve & Bueno, 2012) that almost half of the immigrants arrived single to Spain. As half of the immigrants marry after their arrival, it becomes a point of interest to know whether that marriage is endogamous or exogamous. (Esteve & Bueno, 2012) highlight that Moroccans were the top immigrants in terms of numbers in Spain till 2008, when they got replaced by Rumanians.

It was found out that Moroccans have the highest endogamy rates among immigrants in Spain. This was owed to not just the cultural differences but also to the stark contrast in their nature and rates of wages and employment and also in their religions.

Due to the undocumented migrations and marriages happening inside Spain, there are many people who are born in Spain and share a different origin than Spaniards. Liu et al (2019) mentions the fact that Spain has a rising population with second generation whose origins are not clearly known.

Despite the fact that many of the second generation were born in Spain, they face a lot of challenges and there is still discrimination against them on the basis of many factors. There are many authors who have the

opinion that some historical relation affects the mentality towards foreigners. Therefore, migrants from South America are somehow 'preferred' over other migrant groups.

The locals or natives often despise the immigrants as the common perceptions shape their thinking. The insecurities arise out of fear of loss of jobs or simply because of the lack of opportunities. Spain has seen ups and downs in its economy and hence the scenarios have kept changing regarding the perception about the Moroccan immigrants.

Another aspect that needs to be studied is how Spaniards see themselves. According to (Checa & Garrido, 2012), they prefer ethnic over civic when it comes to their perception of acceptance. They accept those more who were born in Spain or had Spanish blood in them. They don't care about being a Spanish citizen or just living in Spain.

(Checa & Garrido, 2012) have also classified the people of Spain into three categories; utilitarian, differentialist and pluralist. The utilitarians only see immigrants as a work force. The differentialist can't see them without their ethnic identity. And finally, the pluralists who are few in numbers, are more tolerant and accept the foreign population.

Conclusion

The relationship between Spain and Morocco is deeply influenced by their geographies, shared history and complex geopolitics. Migration has always been one of the prime factors influencing their bilateral relations, socio political scenarios and economic evolution. While historical ties, such as the shared influence of Arab and other cultures on Spain, have fostered a unique connection, modern realities of migration have added layers of complexity to their relations.

The conflicts that are of territorial nature or the sociocultural ones that are exacted within the Spanish territory are the reflection of the rising global trend in migration politics. It is this migration politics that gives birth to policies like the one of 'ley de extranjería' enacted in the past. The duality in the perception and the real effect of migration is also exposed when there is actual shortage of immigrant labourers and a constant threat to national security and social integration is claimed on the other hand. No matter what policies are enacted, the importance of Morocco and its role as both a source and transit point for migrants underscores its strategic significance in regional geopolitics.

Cultural exchanges and demographic shifts have also left indelible marks on both nations. The high rates of endogamy among Moroccan immigrants, the rise of a second generation of Spaniards with Moroccan roots, and the linguistic and cultural commonalities serve as reminders of the enduring interconnectedness between these two societies. However, persistent issues of discrimination and socio-economic inequality continue to challenge the narrative of integration.

Morocco-Spain relations will continue to evolve as they will also need to address the challenges through cooperation, understanding and accepting migration as not just a policy issue but also a point of cultural contact and economic progress. It is through investing time and resources on research based on the historical and cultural ties, Morocco and Spain can build a future with equal partnership and trust. That trust and partnership will go a long way in benefiting their citizens and address the challenges and complexities of contemporary migration.

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